

THE PRIME NUMBER SERIES 31

No Fermat pseudoprime of the form u^2-2 to base 2

Theorem.

There exists no composite odd number

$$U = u^2 - 2 \quad (u \geq 3 \text{ odd}),$$

for which

$$2^{U-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{U}$$

holds.

Proof.

We carry out the proof by contradiction.

Assume that there exists a composite odd number

$$U = u^2 - 2$$

with

$$2^{U-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{U}.$$

Then U is a Fermat pseudoprime to base 2. For every prime divisor $p \mid U$ we have

$$\text{ord}_p(2) \mid (U - 1) = u^2 - 3. \quad (1)$$

From $p \mid u^2 - 2$ follows

$$u^2 \equiv 2 \pmod{p},$$

thus 2 is a quadratic residue modulo p . Thus it holds

$$\left(\frac{2}{p}\right) = 1,$$

and by the law of quadratic reciprocity

$$p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{8}. \quad (2)$$

Since u is odd, we have $u^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, therefore

$$p \equiv u^2 - 2 \equiv 7 \pmod{8}.$$

In particular $(p - 1)/2$ is odd. Because 2 is a square modulo p , follows

$$\text{ord}_p(2) \mid (p - 1)/2. \quad (3)$$

From (1) and (3) we obtain

$$\text{ord}_p(2) \mid \gcd(u^2 - 3, (p - 1)/2). \quad (4)$$

Lemma. For every prime divisor $p \mid (u^2 - 2)$ we have

$$\gcd(u^2 - 3, (p - 1)/2) = 1.$$

Proof of the Lemma.

From $p \mid u^2 - 2$ exists a $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ with

$$u^2 = 2 + k p,$$

thus

$$u^2 - 3 = k p - 1.$$

Let

$$d = \gcd(u^2 - 3, (p - 1)/2).$$

Then we have

$$d \mid (k p - 1), \quad d \mid (p - 1)/2.$$

From $d \mid (p - 1)/2$ follows

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{2d}. \quad (5)$$

Reduction of $u^2 = 2 + k p$ modulo d yields, because of (5)

$$u^2 \equiv 2 + k \pmod{d}. \quad (6)$$

On the other hand, it follows from $d \mid (u^2 - 3)$

$$u^2 \equiv 3 \pmod{d}. \quad (7)$$

From (6) and (7) follows
 $k \equiv 1 \pmod{d}$.

Thus it holds

$$k p - 1 \equiv p - 1 \pmod{d}.$$

Because $d \mid (k p - 1)$, follows $d \mid (p - 1)$. Because $(p - 1)/2$ is odd, it follows
 $d \mid \gcd(p - 1, (p - 1)/2) = 1$,
thus $d = 1$.

From (4) and the lemma it follows

$$\text{ord}_p(2) = 1,$$

thus

$$2 \equiv 1 \pmod{p},$$

which is impossible for a prime number $p > 1$.

The contradiction shows that the assumption was false. Thus there exists no composite odd number of the form

$$U = u^2 - 2,$$

that is a Fermat pseudoprime to base 2.

Munich, 11 January 2026

Gottfried Färberböck